

ABSTRACT: The composites are mainly composed of two parts: polymer matrix and rigid reinforcement. Traditionally, the matrix resins depend heavily on petroleum resources which is rapidly depleting and also cause many environmental problems. The Affordable Composites from Renewable Resources (ACRES) program at the University of Delaware has developed a broad range of polymers from natural plant oils. These low cost, biodegradable, high performance resins open a big market on new bio-based materials which would have significant economic advantage and environmental impact. Triglycerides are the main component of natural plant and animal oils. Triglycerides are three-armed stars composed of three fatty acids joined at a glycerol juncture. Most common fatty acids range in length from 16 to 22 carbons long with unsaturation varying from 0-3 double bonds. Numerous synthetic routes have been developed to synthesize monomers which can copolymerize with other co monomers, such as styrene and methyl methacrylate to form rigid thermoset resins with a wide range of physical properties. These polymers exhibit flexural strength in the range of 50-100 MPa, flexural modulus 1.5-3.0 GPa and glass transition temperature 70-160 °C. These resins are suitable for the general liquid molding process, and one specialty is the development of new sheet molding compounds (SMC) resins which have comparable properties with commercial unsaturated polyester. It was demonstrated that these new SMC resins show thickening behavior with divalent metal oxides and good compatibility with commercial low profile additives. Lignin was successfully modified to enforce these polymer matrices, which can contribute to the use of the waste product. Nanocomposites have attracted much interest in recent 10 years since the development of a nylon-6/clay nanocomposite by Toyota researchers. New bio-based nanocomposites were developed using these triglycerides-based polymers, carbon nanotube and organo-treated clays. The multi-walled nanotubes were prepared by the arc discharge method in Trinity College, Dublin, Ireland. Initial study showed that the nanotubes can disperse in these polymer matrices very well and significantly increase the mechanical properties. Organo-treated clays were also used to enforce the polymer matrix. Both XRD and TEM confirmed the formation of nanocomposites. Flexural modulus increased 30% at only 4 vol % clay content, but there is no significant effect on flexural strength and glass transition temperature. This work is supported by NSF, DOE and EPA.

KEYWORDS: Triglyceride, thermosetting resins, lignin, clay nanocomposites

INTRODUCTION

Polymers and composites materials are widely used in various field, such as aerospace, automotive, marine, infrastructure, military, sports and industrial fields. The recently emerged nanocomposites even broaden their applications in many field. With relatively low loading of nanometer-sized particles, they showed dramatically increased stiffness, HDT, dimensional stability, gas barrier, electrical conductivity and flame retardancy [1,2]. Most of composites matrices are derived from petroleum resources. With the fast depleting of these resources, replacing some or all of these with readily available, renewable and

exploratory work was also done to synthesize these plant oil based nanocomposites. These low cost, biodegradable, high performance polymers and composites open a big market on new bio-based materials which would have significant economic advantage and environmental impact.

Plant oils are mainly composed of triglyceride molecules, which have the structure shown in Fig. 1. Triglycerides contain three fatty acids connected by a glycerol center through ester linkages. The fatty acids in most common triglycerides have 0 to 3 double bonds and vary from 14 to 22 carbons in length [5]. While the double bond is the main functionality present on a fatty acid, other functionalities, such as epoxies, hydroxides, cyclic groups, and furanoid groups also occur naturally [6]. Plant oils have been widely used in coatings, inks, plasticizers, lubricants and agrochemicals except in the food industry [7-11]. Some work has been done to use epoxidized plant oils as toughening agent in epoxy matrix [12,13]. Interpenetrating networks (IPNs) based on functionalized triglycerides has also been extensively studied [14,15]. In all these applications, triglyceride was a minor component in the polymer matrix. In recent years, extensive work has been done to develop polymers for engineering applications using plant oils as the main component [3,4,16-24]. Li and coworkers [21-23,25] developed a series of polymers ranging from rubbery to rigid by cationic polymerization of different kinds of oils with styrene and divinyl benzene. Another approach to make plant oil based polymers is to introduce polymerizable functionalities onto the triglycerides molecule. Polyurethane networks from triglycerides have been well studied [18,24]. In our previous work, we have presented many synthetic pathways to develop a broad range of polymers and composites from plants oils [3,4]. Multifunctional triglycerides are produced using active sites which are amenable to chemical reaction, such as the double bonds and the ester groups, then styrene or other co-monomers are added as reactive diluents. Very detailed synthetic pathways and experimental methods can be found elsewhere [3,4]. In this work, we focus on three triglyceride monomers, shown in Fig. 1, they are acrylated epoxidized soybean oil (AESO), maleinized acrylated epoxidized soybean oil (MAESO) and soybean oil pentaerythritol maleates (SOPERMA). These monomers, when used as a major component of a molding resin, have shown properties comparable to conventional thermosetting polymers.

1. Synthesis and applications of triglyceride-based monomers

AESO is synthesized from the reaction of acrylic acid with epoxidized triglycerides. AESO has been used extensively in the area of surface coatings and is commercially manufactured in forms such as Ebecryl 860 (UCB Chemical Company) [9]. AESO can also be blended with a reactive diluent, such as styrene to produce polymers with different moduli and glass transition temperature (T_g). As a result of the acrylation reaction, the triglycerides contain both unreacted epoxy ring as well as newly formed hydroxyl groups, both of which can be used to further modify the triglyceride by reaction with a number of chemical species (e.g., diacids, diamine, anhydrides, and isocyanates). MAESO was synthesized by reaction of the AESO with maleic anhydride which introduced more reactive double bonds as well as carboxylic acid functionality. MAESO, when blended with styrene, can be used in sheet molding compounds (SMC) applications as commercial unsaturated polyester [19,26]. An essential feature of the SMC process is the maturation of thickening of resin compositions [27]. MAESO was proven to have a good thickening behavior and comparable mechanical properties with unsaturated polyesters [19].

Triglyceride Molecule

AESO

Pentaerythritol glyceride tris-maleate half ester

MAESO

Monoglyceride bis-maleate half ester

SOPERMA

Monomers from plant oils can also be prepared by reducing the triglyceride oil to monoglycerides using the standard glycerolysis reaction and followed by a reaction with maleic anhydride. The detailed synthetic pathway can be found elsewhere [3,16,17]. As an improvement, we present a new method which uses pentaerythritol instead of glycerol. The reaction offers certain advantages such as the presence of higher number of hydroxyl groups and therefore, more reactive sites for maleinization and the presence of only primary hydroxyls which are more reactive in maleinization than the secondary hydroxyls of glycerol [28,29]. Castor oil, which has naturally occurred hydroxyl groups, was also used. When blended with styrene, the resulting polymers showed improved mechanical properties.

2. Lignin as a property enhancing additive

Lignin is one of the three most abundant renewable resources in the world amid cellulose and natural oils [30]. Lignin is found in all cellulose bearing plants. Despite its widespread availability, industrial applications of lignin are still very limited. Lignin has been used as a replacement for phenol in phenolic resins because of its polyphenolic structure [31]. It has also been added to epoxy resin, polyurethanes, acrylics and some thermoplastics with varying success [32,33]. Previous work of using kraft lignin as an additive to triglycerides-based thermosetting resins has shown a significant decrease in mechanical properties [34]. This was due to lignin's capability to inhibit free radical polymerization by formation of quinonic structures and its incompatibility with styrene [35]. In this work, the hydroxyl groups of lignin were modified with butyric anhydride. The resulting kraft lignin has better compatibility with styrene and is incapable to form quinonic structures.

increase in the mechanical properties. In this work, we focus on the synthesis and characterization of clay nanocomposites, as the clay is favored for the principle of reducing material cost. Polymer-layered silicate nanocomposites have been extensively studied with conventional polymers [1,2,36-39]. The extreme large surface area and high aspect ratio (between 30 and 2000) are largely responsible for the property improvements resulting from the formation of a nanocomposite. There are essentially three different approaches to synthesize polymer-clay nanocomposite: melt intercalation, solution and in situ polymerization. The synthesis of nanocomposite using triglyceride-based resins is included in the last category, as are epoxy resins and unsaturated polyester resins. The nanocomposites are prepared by first swelling the organo-modified montmorillonite (MMT) with the monomers, followed by cross-linking reactions. It is believed that the exfoliation of silicate layers are related to the polarity of the monomers [40]. An intercalated structure is formed when polymerize nonpolar styrene with clay [37], but most epoxy-based nanocomposites show an exfoliated structure [40,41]. Several studies have shown the formation of partial exfoliated morphology for UP/clay nanocomposites [36,42]. Since triglyceride-based monomers have polar groups such as hydroxyl and acid groups, these molecules are favored in the formation of a possible exfoliated structure. Triglycerides also offer the ability to control the number of polar groups by chemistry approach. In this study, we report the morphology and properties of these new triglyceride-based nanocomposites.

EXPERIMENTAL

1. Synthesis of MAESO

AESO was obtained in the form of Ebecry-860 (UCB Radcure Inc.) This AESO is fully acrylated with approximately 3.4 acrylates per triglyceride and average molecular weight of 1200 g/mol. Maleic anhydride, N, N-Dimethylbenzylamine (BDMA), hydroquinone, styrene were all obtained from the Aldrich Chemical Co, and used as received. To synthesize MAESO, 50 g of AESO and 0.05 g of hydroquinone were first heated to 70 °C, while being stirred. 8.17 g maleic anhydride was added to the reaction mixture at 70 °C. The mixture was then heated up to 80-85 °C, at which point the maleic anhydride dissolved, forming a homogeneous solution. 1 g of BDMA catalyst was then added. The reaction was stopped after 6 hours before gelation occurred.

2. Synthesis of SOPERMA (COPERMA)

In the alcoholysis reaction, 400g of soybean oil was mixed with 186.51g pentaerythritol (Aldrich) and 5.87g Ca(OH)₂ in a three necked 1L round bottom flask equipped with a mechanical stirrer and a nitrogen gas inlet, calcium drier. The reaction mixture was heated to 230-240 °C and agitated under N₂ atmosphere for two hours. The reaction product at room temperature was a light brown colored viscous liquid which separated into two layers. In the maleinization reaction, 540g of soybean oil pentaerythritol alcoholysis product and 311.86 g of maleic anhydride were placed in a 1L flask equipped with a thermometer and a mechanical stirrer. The mixture was heated in an oil bath with stirring until maleic anhydride melted and mixed with the soybean oil pentaerythritol alcoholysis product. Then 8.52 g BDMA and 0.852g of hydroquinone were added and the reaction mixture was heated to 95 °C. The mixture was agitated at this temperature for two hours. Both the IR and the H-NMR spectroscopy of the product confirmed the consumption of maleic anhydride and the formation of maleate halfesters. Castor oil

The copolymerization of AESO, MAESO, SOPERMA with styrene were all run under similar conditions for comparison. 67 wt% triglycerides-based monomer and 33 wt % styrene were well mixed. tert-Butyl peroxy benzoate (TBP) radical initiator (Elf Atochem), 2 % by weight of the total mixture was added. N₂ gas was purged for 5 min. The solution was then transferred into a rectangular rubber gasket mold that was sandwiched between two steel plates. The resin was cured at 110 °C for 2 hours and post-cured at 150 °C for 2 hours. The polymer samples were then polished and prepared for DMA. DMA was conducted in a three-point bending geometry on a Rheometrics Solids Analyzer II (Rheometric Scientific Inc.). Temperature ramps were run from 30 to 180 °C at a ramp rate of 5 °C/min with a frequency of 1 Hz and strain of 0.01%. The flexural properties were measured in accordance with ASTM D 790.

4. Lignin modification and polymerization

Hardwood lignin PC-1369 (WestVaco) was used. Kraft lignin and butyric anhydride (Sigma-Aldrich) were added in a 1-2 weigh ratio to an Erlenmeyer flask. Per 40 g of lignin, 1 g of 1-Methyl Imidazole (Sigma Aldrich) was added. The reaction mixture was heated up to 50 °C and reacted for several hours while stirring vigorously. The extents of butyration was checked with an AC250 250-MHz NMR-spectrometer. Ethyl ether (Fisher Scientific) was then added to the reaction mixture to remove the catalyst. This mixture was washed with deionized water three times. Lignin was sedimented out of the ethyl ether/BA/lignin mixture with cyclohexane (Fisher Scientific). The sedimented lignin was then filtered out and left under vacuum for 24 hrs to dry. After drying, the appropriate amount of lignin was pre-dissolved in styrene and stirred until completely dissolved. AESO was then added to give the desired weight ratio's (AESO/styrene=70/30). 1 wt % TBP was added and mixed well. The mixture was purged with nitrogen for 5 min to remove all oxygen. It was cured at 110 °C for 2 hours and post cured at 160 °C for 2 hours. DMA was conducted in a three-point bending geometry on a Rheometrics Solids Analyzer II (Rheometric Scientific Inc.). The flexural properties and fracture toughness were measured in accordance with ASTM D 790 and ASTM D 5045, respectively.

5. Synthesis and characterization of clay nanocomposites

Cloisite[®] 30B, a natural montmorillonite modified with methyl tallow bis-2-hydroxyethyl quaternary ammonium chloride was obtained from Southern Clay Products. Several different clay concentrations in the triglycerides-based resins were investigated (3, 5, 7.5, 10 wt % based on the total weight of the resin). The desired amount of clay was added to the resin and mechanically stirred for 24-48 h with the flask well sealed to prevent the evaporation of styrene. Both room temperature and high temperature curing was used to cure the sample. For the high temperature curing, 1.5 wt % TBP was added and the mixture was cured at 110 °C for 3 h and post cured at 150 °C for 2 h. For RT-curing, 3 wt % of trigonox 239A (Akzo Nobel) and 0.8 wt % of Cobalt Naphthalate was added. Samples were cured at room temperature for 24 h and then post cured at 150 °C for 2 h. Wide-angle X-ray diffraction measurements were performed on the solid samples with a Philips X'Pert diffractometer using Cu K α radiation in the 2 θ range 0-10°. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was performed on a JEOL 2000 FX electron microscope on 100 nm thick sections, microtomed from the cured samples. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was performed using a TA instruments thermogravimetric analyzer Q500 with samples being heated to 600 °C under He atmosphere at a heating rate of 20 °C /min. DMA was conducted in a three-point bending

Fig. 3 E' and tan delta of MAESO compared with AESO polymer

Fig. 4 Dynamic mechanical behavior of SOPERMA polymers

them to be incorporated into the polymer. The DMA of COPERMA/styrene polymers showed a $\tan\delta$ peak at $\sim 158^\circ\text{C}$ and E' value of 3.74 GPa at 30°C . We can see there is a considerable increase on the storage

1. Viscoelastic and mechanical properties of triglyceride-based polymers

Fig. 2 shows the temperature dependence of the storage modulus E' , loss modulus E'' and the loss factor $\tan\delta$ for AESO/styrene polymer. In general, this polymer shows a broad transition from the glassy to the rubbery state, which is due to the plasticizing characteristics of saturated fatty acids in the network and different molecular structure of AESO compared to the aromatic styrene. The polymer has a storage modulus of approximately 1.1 GPa at room temperature, and a $\tan\delta$ peak at 71°C . The modification of AESO with maleic anhydride provides more cross-link sites per triglycerides as it adds maleate functionality on the triglyceride and increases the molecular weight by condensation reaction. Fig. 3 shows the temperature dependence of the storage modulus and $\tan\delta$ behavior of the MAESO polymer compared with AESO polymers. Clearly, both storage modulus and glass transition temperature are increased significantly with maleic anhydride modification. The transition from glassy to rubbery is also broadened by the addition of maleic anhydride, which is contributed by the increased cross-link density and heterogeneity of the molecular structure in the MAESO resin.

The dynamic mechanical behavior of the SOPERMA/styrene polymer is shown in Fig. 4. The $\tan\delta$ peak occurs at 155°C and the polymer has an E' value of ~ 1.27 GPa. It is apparent that the glass transition is rather broad due to the broad MW distribution of the SOPER maleates which contains pentaerythritol glyceride tris-maleates and monoglyceride bis-maleates, and also the plasticizing effect of saturated fatty acids. In an effort to reduce the plasticizing effect, castor oil was used instead of soybean oil in the same formulation (COPERMA). Castor oil contains 87% by weight ricinoleic acid which has hydroxyl groups. Therefore, the maleinization of these hydroxyl groups will allow

Table 1 summarizes both the viscoelastic and flexural properties of three triglyceride-based polymers. For comparison, a commercial petroleum-based unsaturated polyester is included in Table 1. Their properties are very comparable.

Table 1 The mechanical properties of the plant oil based polymers

Resin	E' (30 °C) (GPa)	tan δ_{\max} (°C)	Flexural Modulus (GPa)	Flexural Strength (MPa)
AESO	1.10	71	1.9	40
MAESO	1.93	114	2.04	83.44
SOPERMA	1.27	155	1.27	55.77
COPERMA	3.74	158	2.49	111.97
Ortho-UPE		~130	3.45	80

2. Lignin modification

Fig. 5 shows both flexural modulus and strength go through a maximum with increasing amount of butyrate lignin (PC-BA) in AESO/styrene polymer matrix. This does not agree with regular filler effect. The appearance of a maximum can be explained on the molecular scale. At low lignin concentrations, lignin has a positive contribution to the modulus and strength due to the introduction of a stiffer molecule. At higher loads, the increase is being offset by the decrease in cross-link density, which results in a drop in mechanical properties. DMA analysis found the glass transition temperature to increase to a plateau value, reached at around 7.5 wt % lignin, besides the linear decrease in cross-link density. The plateau value is ~61 °C, which is much lower than the glass transition temperature of around 140 °C reported for unmodified lignin. Fig. 6 shows the K_{Ic} values from fracture toughness analysis. As expected, with

Fig. 5 Flexural properties vs. Lignin-BA concentration

Fig. 6 Fracture toughness vs. lignin-BA concentration

increasing the lignin-BA concentration, the plane strain fracture toughness increases almost linearly due to the plasticizing effect of lignin itself. G_{Ic} also increases linearly with increasing the lignin-BA

nanocomposite system

The X-ray scattering data for the organically modified clay, Cloisite® 30B (C30B) and MAESO/styrene nanocomposites containing different concentrations of clay are shown in Fig. 7. Pure C30B shows an significant peak at 4.85° corresponding to a d-spacing of 18.2 Å (a). This peak disappears for the 3 wt % C30B in MAESO matrix (b). When the concentration of C30B goes up to 10 wt % (c), there are two peaks: 5.71° and 1.24° corresponding to a d-spacing of 15.5 Å and 71.4 Å, respectively. XRD data confirms the formation of an exfoliated structure at low clay concentration but an intercalated structure at high clay loads. The samples prepared with AESO and SOPERMA showed very

similar behavior. More direct evidence for the formation of nanocomposites is provided by TEM of a thin section (100 nm). Fig. 8a shows well-dispersed individual silicate layers and some small bundles for 3 wt % C30B in AESO matrix. When clay concentration goes up to 5 wt % (Fig. 8b), the micro-sized aggregates of sheets are still preserved although the individual sheets of clay are separated by a layer of polymer observed at higher magnification. MAESO-based nanocomposites show very similar morphology, but TEM showed a much better dispersion of clay in SOPERMA matrix even at 5 wt % C30B, this is due to the low molecular weight and high polarity (acid number > 200) of SOPERMA which allow the molecules to penetrate into clay layers more readily.

Fig. 8 TEM micrographs of AESO/C30B nanocomposite systems

Fig. 9 Flexural properties vs. clay concentration

The DMA analysis showed an increase of 9% and 20% in storage modulus for 3 wt % C30B in AESO and SOPERMA matrices, respectively. The T_g is slightly lowered. The higher increase for SOPERMA/C30B can be explained by the morphology. Fig. 9 shows the dependence of the flexural properties of MAESO nanocomposites on the clay content. As expected, the flexural modulus increases

to the inhomogeneity of the structure and imperfect bonding. The flexural strength increases slightly with increasing clay content and then decreases. TGA showed the thermal degradation is slightly hastened by the formation of nanocomposites.

CONCLUSIONS

The use of natural resources such as triglyceride oils, lignin in polymers and composites offers economic and environmental advantages. The functionalized triglycerides, when blended with comonomers, form polymers with a wide range of physical properties. They exhibit moduli in the 1-2.5 GPa range and T_g ranging from 70 to 160 °C. DMA shows that the transition from the glassy to rubbery behavior is broad for these polymers due to the high cross-link density and plasticizing effect of the saturated fatty acids in the system. The use of castor oil with hydroxyl groups incorporates most saturated fatty acids chains into the polymer network, which dramatically increases the mechanical properties of the resulting polymers. The modification of lignin with butyric anhydride increases the solubility of lignin in styrene. Small addition of lignin-BA to AESO/styrene resin systems can have a significant effect on mechanical properties, and it also increases the renewable content of these thermosets. At an optimized level with only 5 wt % lignin-BA in AESO/styrene, the flexural modulus and strength increases 75% and 60%, respectively, both K_{1c} and G_{1c} increases 50% as the results of the lignin molecules acting both as stiffer molecules and plasticizer in the system. The formation of nanocomposites based on these triglyceride-based resins has been confirmed both by the X-ray data and transmission electron microscopy. It is found the monomers with high polarity are favored in forming exfoliated structure. The morphology shows a mix of intercalated and partially exfoliated sheets. The formation of nanocomposites significantly increases flexural modulus but no significant effect on flexural strength and glass transition temperature.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank NSF, DOE and EPA for funding.

REFERENCES

1. Alexandre, M. and Dubois, P. (2000). *Materials Science & Engineering R-Reports* **28**: 1-63.
2. LeBaron, P.C., Wang, Z., and Pinnavaia, T.J. (1999). *Applied Clay Science* **15**: 11-29.
3. Wool, R.P., Kusefoglu, S.H., Palmese, G.R., Zhao, R., and Khot, S.N. (2000). U.S. Patent 6,121,398.
4. Khot, S.N., Lascala, J.J., Can, E., Morye, S.S., Williams, G.I., Palmese, G.R., Kusefoglu, S.H., and Wool, R.P. (2001). *Journal of Applied Polymer Science* **82**: 703-723.
5. Liu, K. (1997). *Soybeans: Chemistry, Technology, and Utilization*, Chapman and Hall, New York.
6. Gunstone, F. (1996). *Fatty Acid and Lipid Chemistry*, 1st Ed., Blackie Academic and Professional, New York.
7. Cunningham, A. and Yapp, A. (1974). U.S. Patent 3,827,993.
8. Bussell, G.W. (1974). U.S. Patent 3,855,163.
9. Hodakowski, L.E., Osborn, C.L., and Harris, E.B. (1975). U.S. Patent 4,119,640.
10. Salunkhe, D.K., Chavan, J.K., Adsule, R.N., and Kadam, S.S. (1992). *World Oilseeds: Chemistry, Technology, and Utilization*, Van Nostrand Reinhold, New York.
11. Trecker, D.J., Borden, G.W., and Smith, O.W. (1976). U.S. Patent 3,931,075.
12. Frischinger, I. and Dirlikov, S. (1993). *Advances in Chemistry Series*: 451-489.

15. Barrett, L.W., Sperling, L.H., and Murphy, C.J. (1993). *Journal of the American Oil Chemists' Society* **70**: 523-534.
16. Can, E., Kusefoglou, S., and Wool, R.P. (2001). *Journal of Applied Polymer Science* **81**: 69-77.
17. Can, E., Kusefoglou, S., and Wool, R.P. (2002). *Journal of Applied Polymer Science* **83**: 972-980.
18. Guo, A., Demydov, D., Zhang, W., and Petrovic, Z.S. (2002). *Journal of Polymers and the Environment* **10**: 49-52.
19. Wool, R.P., Lu, J., and Khot, S.N. (2001). U.S. Patent pending.
20. Wool, R.P. (2002). *Abstracts of Papers of the American Chemical Society* **223**: 082-PMSE.
21. Li, F.K. and Larock, R.C. (2000). *Journal of Polymer Science Part B-Polymer Physics* **38**: 2721-2738.
22. Li, F.K. and Larock, R.C. (2000). *Journal of Applied Polymer Science* **78**: 1044-1056.
23. Li, F.K., Perrenoud, A., and Larock, R.C. (2001). *Polymer* **42**: 10133-10145.
24. Petrovic, Z.S., Zhang, W., Zlatanovic, A., Lava, C.C., and Ilavsky, M. (2002). *Journal of Polymers and the Environment* **10**: 5-12.
25. Li, F.K. and Larock, R.C. (2001). *Journal of Polymer Science Part B-Polymer Physics* **39**: 60-77.
26. Lu, J., Khot, S.N., and Wool, R.P. (2003). In preparation.
27. Kia, H.G. (ed) (1993). *Sheet Molding Compounds Science and Technology*, Hanser/Gardner Publications, Inc., Cincinnati.
28. Can, E. (2003), Personal Communication.
29. Wool, R.P. and Can, E. (2002). U.S. Patent pending.
30. Sarkanen, S.V. (1971). *Lignins: Occurrence, Formation, Structure and Reactions*, Wiley Interscience, New York.
31. Nada, A.M.A., Elsaied, H., Ibrahim, A.A., and Yousef, M.A. (1987). *Journal of Applied Polymer Science* **33**: 2915-2924.
32. Feldman, D. and Lacasse, M. (1994). *Journal of Adhesion Science and Technology* **8**: 957-969.
33. Feldman, D., Banu, D., Lacasse, M., Wang, J., and Luchian, C. (1995). *Journal of Macromolecular Science-Pure and Applied Chemistry* **A32**: 1613-1619.
34. Thielemans, W., Can, E., Morye, S.S., and Wool, R.P. (2002). *Journal of Applied Polymer Science* **83**: 323-331.
35. Thielemans, W. and Wool, R.P. (2002). In: *Proceedings of AIChE*. Indianapolis, Indian.
36. Bharadwaj, R.K., Mehrabi, A.R., Hamilton, C., Trujillo, C., Murga, M., Fan, R., Chavira, A., and Thompson, A.K. (2002). *Polymer* **43**: 3699-3705.
37. Doh, J.G. and Cho, I. (1998). *Polymer Bulletin* **41**: 511-518.
38. Giannelis, E.P., Krishnamoorti, R., and Manias, E. (1999) in: *Polymers in Confined Environments* Vol. 138, pp. 107-147.
39. Weimer, M.W., Chen, H., Giannelis, E.P., and Sogah, D.Y. (1999). *Journal of the American Chemical Society* **121**: 1615-1616.
40. Kornmann, X., Lindberg, H., and Berglund, L.A. (2001). *Polymer* **42**: 4493-4499.
41. Lan, T. and Pinnavaia, T.J. (1994). *Chemistry of Materials* **6**: 2216-2219.
42. Kornmann, X., Berglund, L.A., and Sterte, J. (1998). *Polymer Engineering and Science* **38**: 1351-1358.